

DISSERTATION

Relation between social media usage and cyber victimization in adolescent

Bachelor of Arts in Psychology (Hors.)

A Dissertation Submitted by

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Acknowledgement

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to the following individuals and institutions who have supported and contributed to the completion of this dissertation. First and foremost, I am immensely grateful to my guide, Dr. Kirti Prashant Barad, for their unwavering guidance, valuable insights, and continuous encouragement throughout this research journey. Their expertise and dedication have greatly helped in shaping the direction and quality of this dissertation. I want to express my gratitude to our regional director, Dr. E. Krishna Rao, and the staff of the regional center in Mumbai, Shri. P. Namboothiripal (Assistant Regional Director), Sri.Vijaykumar M. (Assistant Registrar), Shri Sanjay Kumar (JAT), and Shri. Shashank Raghvendra Tripathi (JAT). I express my gratitude towards K. J. Somaiya College of Art and Commerce, whose lectures, seminars, and discussions have broadened my knowledge base and inspired me to pursue this research. Their commitment to excellence in education and passion for the subject matter have been a constant motivation source.

My deep gratitude to my family for their unconditional love, unwavering support, and understanding during this challenging endeavor. Their belief in my abilities and their encouragement has been my pillar of strength throughout. Lastly, I would like to acknowledge the participants of this study who generously dedicated their time and shared their insights. Their contributions have been invaluable in shaping the findings and conclusions of this dissertation. While I have made every effort to acknowledge everyone contributing to this dissertation, I may have unintentionally omitted someone. I sincerely apologize for any oversight and assure you that your contribution is greatly appreciated. The dissertation would not have been completed without these individuals' and institutions' collective support and collaboration. Thank you all for your invaluable contributions and for being an integral part of this research journey.

Ami Nhawkar

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Synopsis

1. Introduction:

“Unless and until our society recognizes cyberbullying for what it is, the suffering of thousands of silent victims will continue” Anna Maria Chavez.

Due to the abundance of technology available to kids today, cyberbullying has increased in prevalence. Parents and teachers are not aware of when and where it is occurring, stopping has become more challenging. An MBBS student in Kerala committed suicide by jumping from the top floor of her college building. Her Facebook profile revealed that she was upset about the negative remarks made by one of her peers. Police believe she was motivated to take this drastic action by cyberbullying (Shree, 2017). Victimization by cyberbullying is regarded as a global public health problem affecting adolescents' psychological growth, which frequently lasts into adulthood. Given the dearth of such studies in low-resource settings like India, the current study examined the long-term relationships between cyberbullying victimization and depression and suicidal ideation among adolescents and young adults (Wright, 2022).

According to Gagan Singh, Chief Product officer at McAfee Corp., cyberbullying in India has reached alarming levels. Over one-third of children experience sexual harassment, cyber racism, and threats of physical harm as early as age 10. This makes India the top country for reported cyberbullying in the world. According to a survey by the international computer security company McAfee Corp., the percentage of children in India who have reported experiencing cyberbullying is approximately 85%, making it the highest globally (Vats, 2022). The pandemic increased the number of cases of online harassment. 257 Indian cities submitted over 900 complaints to the anti-cyberbullying platform in 2021. There have been incidents concerning the abuse of images or revenge pornography (TNN, 2022). The results obtained in different scientific studies, show considerable divergence probably due to different methodological measures and strategies used to evaluate cyberbullying and cyber-victimization (Sofia Buelga, 2019). This study is significant because there has not been much

research in this area for individuals from India. The two variables under this study are social media usage and cyber victimization.

2. Literature review

2.1. Prevalence

The 'Cyberbullying in Plain Sight' survey study is based on a 10-country to uncover new and "consequential trends" regarding cyberbullying. They surveyed 14 social media sites, from Facebook and Instagram to Snapchat. It was discovered that Indian children reported experiencing cyberbullying on online platforms up to 1.5 times more frequently than children in other countries. The survey also found that only 46% of Indian children told their parents about being the victims of cyberbullying, significantly less than the global average of 64%, "possibly due to the relative absence of conversation" about the subject. According to the survey, Indian kids were dealing with cyberbullying on their own in the absence of dialogue and encouragement. To prevent cyberbullying, nearly three out of five children (58%) said they deleted their social media accounts, and 87% said they talked to their friends about it (Vats, 2022).

2.2. Effects

The "Understanding the Lives of Adolescents and Young Adults" (UDAYA- 2015–2016 and 2018–2019) surveys were conducted in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar. Over three years, cyberbullying victimization rose among female respondents from 3.8% to 6.4% and among male respondents from 1.9% to 5.6%. In their early adulthood, about 33% of women and 16.6% of men reported having depressive symptoms. In the previous year, nearly 7.5% of females and 2.3% of males said they had considered committing suicide. (Wright, 2022). According to Cyber Bullying, Action Awareness Prevention (CBAAP) reports, sextortion is the most common complaint, followed by trolling. The cities where CBAAP received complaints about cyberbullying were New Delhi, Bengaluru, and Mumbai. College and high school students made up a sizable portion (60%) of the complainants. The CBAAP received complaints from some suicidal people. In 2021, men (54%) filed more complaints against CBAAP than women (TNN, 2022).

Younger children and teenagers will feel more alone and depressed, have significant changes in their eating and sleeping patterns, and lose interest in their usual activities if preventive measures against cyberbullying are not taken.

3. Rationale of the study

Although cyberbullying is becoming more common in India, more empirical research must be conducted to inform school-based interventions (Sardesai-Nadkarni, 2021). Cyberbullying has such severe effects on the victim that it is regarded as a global public health issue (Aboujaoude, 2015), (Ferrara, 2018). Additionally, 20% of teenage cyber-victims have admitted to having suicidal thoughts (Van Geel, 2014). Basic facts like gender and developmental differences in cyber victimization experiences are poorly understood because research on this topic is in its infancy. Therefore, action must be taken to comprehend how deeply this issue has permeated our society.

4. Methodology

4.1 Problems and objective

The study aims to find the relationship between social network usage and cyber victimisation.

4.2 Hypotheses

H₀: There is no correlation between social network usage and cyber victimisation.

H₁: There is a correlation between social network usage and cyber victimisation

4.3: Operational definitions

Social networking refers to the online space students use to connect, share, communicate, establish, or maintain a connection with others for academic, entertainment, socialization, etc. (Savita Gupta, 2018). Cyber victimization is how others are victimized through information and communication technologies.

4.4. Sample

An online questionnaire will be created using Google Forms, and the questionnaire link will be distributed via email and WhatsApp to 100 individuals. Convenient sampling and snowball methods will be employed to assess the prevalence. Individuals between 12 to 18 years of age, male and female, are eligible to participate in the study. Individuals should be active on one social media account (Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, Twitter, etc.) and use one messenger application (WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Telegram, Viber, etc.) that they are actively engaged in. The individual should be residing in India.

4.5. Tests and tools

4.5.1: The Social Networking Usage Questionnaire

The Social Networking Usage Questionnaire measures social media usage—academic, entertainment, and socialization—in online spaces. The scale has 19 self-reported items that were measured on a 5-point Likert scale; ratings ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The social networking questionnaire was developed to understand the purposes of social networking usage by students in an Indian context (Savita Gupta, 2018). Academic usage questions are irrelevant to our study; hence, they will be removed from the questionnaire (Holly Reid1 et al., 2021).

4.5.2: Adolescent Cyber-Victimization Scale (CYBVICS)

CYBVICS is an adaptation of the Adolescent Victimization through Mobile Phone and Internet Scale (Sofía Buelga, 2019). This is an updated version of the scale. With the use of smartphone, the distinction between the cell phone and the Internet currently makes no sense. Additionally, this new scale includes eight other items to the items on the original scale. The Cyber-Victimization Scale consists of 18 self-reported items that can rate on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The adolescent's experiences as a victim of cyberbullying in the past 12 months is measured. With a self-report measure, it has a greater capacity to recognize adolescents' cyber-victim behaviors.

4.6. Data Analysis

The Pearson correlation coefficient, a descriptive statistic, will establish both, the magnitude and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables—social media use and cyber victimization. Interpretations will be made with a significance level of $p=0.05$.

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Abstract

Two billion people utilize the platform daily. Cyber victimization—online attacks or harm—has increased with social media use. Cyberbullying, or digital bullying, affects a large number of 11- to 14-year-olds. Despite empirical evidence that spending more time on social media platforms may increase the risk of cyber-victimization, there is little research on how adolescents use social media. A study found that 20% of youth participated in cyberbullying as perpetrators or victims. Social media use has increased cyber victimization among 12-18-year-olds in several nations. This study seeks to correlate two Indian variables. The study examined social media usage and cyber-victimization it is a correlation study that helps identify patterns and relationships between variables. It also illuminates complex phenomena and future research. This study examines the hypothesis that social media use causes cyberbullying. Results show that cyber victimization is rare and mild. The correlation coefficient between the scales is 0.78, indicating a strong positive link. The association is statistically insignificant because the p-value of 0.4 surpasses the 0.05 threshold for statistical significance. This shows that social media use increases online victimization.

Chapter 1

Introduction

In February 2004, at Harvard University, Mark Zuckerberg introduced Facebook. After a few days, 650 students had created accounts. There are currently about two billion users who log on every day. Concern over the mental health of adolescents and young adults has grown along with Facebook's meteoric growth. The suicide rate among 10- to 24-year-olds from 2000 to 2007 was stable. But these figures rose by 57% between 2007 and 2017, as per the Centers for Disease Control data. Given these parallel trends, it is crucial to comprehend the connection between mental health and technology use, mainly how young people use social media (MIT Sloan, 2022).

Social media usage has been associated with a rise in cyber victimization or the act of being attacked or hurt online. There are many types of cyber victimization, including cyberbullying, cyberstalking, identity theft, and harassment. Social media platforms such like Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and Snapchat are now frequently used for online exploitation. Because of their anonymity and accessibility, social media platforms are easier for people to harass and bully others without worrying about the repercussions.

Additionally, social media platforms have disseminated untrue information, rumours, and hate speech, causing the victims psychological and emotional distress. It is crucial to remember that using social media does not automatically lead to online victimization. Instead, it is the abuse of these platforms by those who wish to hurt others. Therefore, it is essential to inform users on how to responsibly use social media. It is important to put policies and regulations in place to prevent and penalize cyber victimization.

Many young adolescents between the ages of 11 and 14 report being victims of cyberbullying (i.e., bullying that occurs online or via technology). Less research has been done on how adolescents use social media, despite evidence that more time spent on social media can increase the likelihood of cyber-victimization. Cyberbullying involves using information and communication technologies to hurt. This includes sending harassing messages (via text or the Internet), posting disparaging comments on a social networking site, posting humiliating pictures, or threatening or intimidating someone electronically (Willard, 2007). Unfortunately, cyberbullying behavior has come to be accepted and expected among adolescents (K. Baker & Helm, 2009). Unlike traditional bullying, cyberbullying is unique because it reaches an unlimited audience with increased exposure across time and space, preserves words and images more permanently (L Nixon, 2022), and lacks supervision. Further, perpetrators of cyberbullying do not see the faces of their targets and subsequently may not understand the full consequences of their actions, thereby decreasing important feelings of personal accountability. This has often been referred to in the literature as the “disinhibition effect” (Suler, 2004).

Bullying existed before the Internet, and mobile phones were created. Many young and adolescent students have bullied others using new technologies, primarily because they believe they can attack while remaining anonymous (anonymity) using these media. This is made possible by other aspects of cyberbullying, such as being unable to see the victim or the suffering and pain caused by the bullying behavior. As a result, they find it much easier to keep their victims at a moral distance. This entails feeling less guilt and scruples when harming another person. Therefore, it should be surprising that cyberbullying prevalence rates have continued to rise.

Online bullies are not concerned with having to deal with the immediate emotional or psychological effects on their victims; because they are separated by technology, which makes it easier to get involved in cyberbullying (McDowell, 2017). Social media usage has been associated with increased cyber victimization, which is the act of being targeted or harmed online. Educating users on responsible social media use and implementing policies and regulations to prevent and punish

cyber victimization is essential. Cyberbullying is a new phenomenon due to young and adolescent students' use of the Internet and cell phones. Neoliberal ideology shapes neoliberal subjects, leading to cyberbullying, a lack of inhibition, and social disengagement.

The primary objective of this research investigation is to scrutinize the conjecture that there exists a correlation between the utilization of social media and the occurrence of cyberbullying. A positive correlation has been observed between the utilization of social media platforms and a heightened incidence of cyber victimization. Social media platforms have emerged as conducive environments for the proliferation of bullying and harassment, owing to their user anonymity and user-friendly interface. It is imperative to bear in mind that falling prey to cybercrime while utilizing social media is not an unavoidable outcome. On the contrary, it is individuals with malicious intentions who engage in the exploitation of these online platforms.

Chapter 2

Review of Literature

2.1 Cyber usage

2.1.1 Internet Usage in India

In the recent years, a significant increase has been seen in the amount of time people spend online in India. This trend is attributed, largely, to the rising affordability of smartphones and mobile data plans. Over 700 million people in India regularly log onto the Internet, making it the second most populous country globally regarding the Internet user base as of 2021. Most people in India who use the Internet do so through their mobile phones; approximately 97% use their mobile phones in India access the Web. Social media sites namely, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and Twitter are also prevalent in India, with millions of users engaging on these platforms daily. This popularity has contributed to the platforms' enormous growth in recent years.

E-commerce is another industry in India that is expanding at a rapid rate, and consumers' preference for conducting their shopping online is only growing. Amazon, Flipkart, and Paytm are some of the notable names in online retailing that can be found in India. However, internet penetration in India is not uniform; rural areas and populations with lower incomes tend to have lower Internet access rates than urban areas and populations with higher incomes. Several programs have been initiated by the government of India to reduce the digital divide and expand Internet access for all its citizens. One of these programs is called the Digital India program, and its primary objective is to bring high-speed Internet access to India's rural areas (Sivakumar, 2021).

According to a report , 432 million people use the Internet in India. However, this does not consider the effects of the demonetization of the currency. By 2017, the number of people in India who use the Internet will fall somewhere in the range between 450 million and 465 million. According to the report, India's internet penetration is estimated at around 31%. The report compared the amount of time spent by people in the Rural and Urban areas of India. The people living in Urban India who use the Internet increased by 7% between October 2015 and October 2016, reaching an estimated 263 million people. By June 2017, the number of users was anticipated to increase to between 272 and 285 million. In the Rural areas of India, the Internet users increased by 22% between October 2015 and October 2016, reaching an estimated 157 million. By June 2017, the number was anticipated to be 170–180 million (IAMAI, 2020). At the beginning of 2023, there were 692.0 million internet users in India, with a 48.7 percent penetration rate (Global Digital Insights,

2023). According to the research, 16.7% of participants have Internet-related problems, and 3.0% are addicted to the Internet (Sneha et al., 2019).

2.1.2 Adolescents and mobile phone ownership the world over

Adolescents and mobile phone ownership are growing trends around the world. According to a report by UNICEF, as of 2020, around 71% of young people aged 15–24 worldwide own a mobile phone. This number is even higher in developed countries, with ownership rates among young people approaching 100%. Several factors, including the increasing affordability of smartphones and mobile data plans, the growing importance of social media and messaging apps in adolescent social life, and the need for access to educational and health-related information, have driven the widespread adoption of mobile phones among adolescents.

While mobile phones can offer many benefits for young people, including increased connectivity, access to information, and opportunities for learning and development, they can also pose risks. These risks include exposure to inappropriate content, cyberbullying, social media, and gaming addiction. Many organizations and governments have developed guidelines and programs to promote safe and responsible mobile phone use among young people to mitigate these risks. These include initiatives to raise awareness about the risks of excessive mobile phone use, parental controls and other technical measures to limit access to inappropriate content, and education programs to promote digital literacy and responsible online behavior.

Mobile phones, especially smartphone usage, are becoming rapidly common among children in several countries worldwide. The rate of ownership, however, varies by nation and age group. The number of children who owned a smartphone in the U.S.A. increased from 35 % in 2011 to 56 % in 2013 (Smith, 2013). Switzerland saw an increase from 47% in 2010 to 79% in 2012. The number of adolescents using mobile phones to surf the Internet increased from 16 % in 2010 to 66 % in 2012. In Germany, 12 to 19-year-old smartphone owners have risen from 25 % in 2011 to 72 % in 2013. In Japan, 47.8 % of junior high and 95.6 % of high school students have mobile phones (Cabinet Office Home Page, n.d.).

A study found that in Chennai, too, out of a sample size of 90 students from 12 different schools and three city colleges, 79 students owned phones. 88.1 % of these children were found to have smartphones. The advantage of reduced call and texting costs could be a reason for the increasing number of smartphone users in this age group. With wireless Internet, smartphones allow adolescents to communicate with peers without charge using Internet-based messenger apps such as

WhatsApp (Lemola et al., 2018). This includes charge-free options to share pictures and short videos with a group of friends.

Furthermore, smartphones also have the advantage of being lighter and handier than notebook computers, permitting their use in bed to surf the Internet or watch videos from YouTube. The availability of the Internet and a plethora of web-based applications on mobile phones pose other grave problems, such as child sex abuse, which cannot be overlooked or forgotten (McCartan & McAlister, n.d.). Additionally, the potential for this population to undergo sexual exploitation is very high because of their online behaviors like sexting and unwittingly involving themselves in the production and distribution of illegal sexually explicit content (McAlister, n.d.).

2.1.3 Unauthorized use of personal data

Using someone else's personal information without their knowledge or consent for purposes they disagreed with is the unauthorized use of personal data. It is a form of data breach. This can include committing identity theft, financial fraud, or other illegal activities using someone else's identifying information like name, phone number, address, social security number etc. The unauthorized use of personal information has developed into a significant problem due to companies and other organizations' proliferation of personal data collection and storage practices.

Hackers and other malicious actors can access data if it is not adequately secured, leading to the theft of personal information and data breach. In many instances, this data needs to be adequately secured. In response to this problem, governments of several nations have passed laws and regulations designed to safeguard the confidentiality of personal information and ensure its safety. In general, these laws require businesses to obtain individuals' consent before collecting and using their personal information, to put appropriate security measures in place to protect that information, and to notify individuals during a data breach. Individuals can also protect their data by taking measures such as using strong passwords, avoiding sharing of sensitive information online or over the phone, and monitoring their credit reports for signs of identity theft or other unauthorized activity. These are examples of the measures individuals can take. Suppose an individual has any reason to believe that the security of their personally identifiable information has been breached. In that case, the appropriate authorities must be notified immediately so as to take corrective measures (Romanosky et al., 2011).

By the beginning of 2008, Choicepoint, a US data aggregation company, had settled numerous class-action lawsuits with significant regulatory fines totaling more than \$25 million (Guthrie,

2023). This was related to a data breach (or leak) in 2004 that affected 160 000 individual records. Around 20 large companies in the United States were simultaneously facing similar legal action and financial penalties for data breaches involving anywhere from 2,000 to 94,000 stolen personal records (DLDOS, 2018). When users submit their data to social networks or third parties operating within social networks, they lose control of these data. They are unaware of the tools used to ensure personal data availability, confidentiality, and integrity. In the absence of information regarding data processing, consumers run the risk of being put in a position vulnerable to threats and risks. This is because their data may be processed by multiple administrators, stored in various geographic areas, or transferred to third parties, which may not provide adequate protection for personal data. (ScienceDirect, 2013).

The Information Technology Act of 2000 provides legal recognition for the transactions carried out employing electronic data interchange and other means of electronic communication. Commonly referred as 'electronic commerce', that provides alternatives to paper-based methods of communication and storage of information, to facilitate electronic filing of documents with government agencies. It further helps to amend the Indian Penal Code, the Indian Evidence Act, 1872, the Bankers' Books Evidence Act, 1891, and the Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934, and for connected matters in addition to or incidental to that.

The General Assembly of the United Nations, resolution A/RES/51/162, dated January 30, 1997, has adopted the Model Law on Electronic Commerce adopted by the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law. The said resolution recommends, among other things, that all States give favorable and whereas consideration to the said Model Law when they enact or revise their laws, because of the need for uniformity of the law applicable to alternatives to paper-based methods of communication and storage of information; and whereas it is considered necessary to give effect to the said resolution and to promote efficient delivery of Government services using reliable electronic records (Central Government Procurement Portal, 2015). Opinion No. 5/2009 on online social networks (from now on, "the Opinion") was produced by the Working Party on Data Protection, established based on Article 29, Directive 95/46/EC. This document is of the utmost importance regarding online social networks. The term "the opinion" will refer to this particular document.

The Working Party on Data Protection, established by Article 29, Directive 95/46/EC, has identified two primary categories of privacy threats and personal data protection. These categories are as follows. The threats posed by this technology are the lack of information on the operations

performed when processing data and the lack of control over the data stored by remote computing. Users who submit their data to social networks or third parties operating in social networks lose control of the data and do not know which tools are used to ensure personal data availability, confidentiality, and integrity.

Users who submit their data to social networks or third parties operating in social networks. Users who share their information with social networks or third parties operating within social networks are at the risk of being in a position where they are vulnerable to threats and risks when there is insufficient information regarding data processing. This is because their personally identifiable information may be processed by multiple administrators, stored in various geographical areas, or transferred to third parties, any or all of which may not provide adequate protection for the personally identifiable information (Limba & Šidlauskas, 2018).

It is noted that although the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party is not legally binding, its contribution is undoubtedly significant in the light of the intention to create a separate legal regulation of online social networks. There is a need to be brought to the attention of every single person. Even though legal regulation is under constant pressure to follow technological progress and, perhaps, in general, is unable to react quickly to rapid changes, the progress made by the Data Protection Working Party is significant and is likely to continue to be successful. This is the case even though legal regulation is constantly pressured to follow technological progress. This is although there is consistent pressure on legal regulation to keep up with the advancement of technology (Štivilis et al., 2012).

The loss of personally identifiable information is both a serious and common problem. According to the most recent database version tracking the loss of personal information, more than 300 million personal records were made public due to more than 900 reported data breaches in the United States. Emerging security concerns for organizations include hacking and accidental leaks on the Internet, as well as the risks that were discussed previously. The expansion of private information gathering is undoubtedly a contributing factor. Another is the increased sharing of personally identifiable information with clients, business partners, and vendors. In addition, workers have greater access to databases, such as file and web servers, and many user-friendly communication channels. (DLDOS, 2018).

2.1.4 CyberSecurity

In today's interconnected world, everything from computers and servers to mobile devices and electronic systems, as well as networks and data, are susceptible to malicious attacks. Cybersecurity refers to protecting networks, systems, and data from attacks of this kind. Alternately, "information technology security" and "electronic information security" are acceptable synonyms for one another and can be used interchangeably. With security concerns being an afterthought in the majority of application domains and the usability of security interventions rarely being taken into consideration, the users are the ones who own the Internet. In every one of these application fields, technology can be found everywhere. The data-centric Internet as it exists today needs to change to emphasize the user experience more. This is especially important because mobile devices are increasingly becoming the focal point of technological design (Conti & Passarella, 2018). The focus should be shifted to protecting users of the Internet from harm that may be caused by cyber security events in order to do justice to the benefits that can arise from the intended usage of technology applications. The benefits arising from the intended usage of technology applications are justified. Because of this, it is possible to fully realize the benefits of utilizing technology applications as intended. With advancements made in the planning and execution of cybersecurity systems, human factors continue to frequently lead to the systems' failure to their fullest extent. There are numerous instances in which users find ways to avoid the security measures that have been put in place to protect them; however, despite the existence of well-organized awareness campaigns, there are still numerous instances in which users find ways to avoid the security measures, or they do not comprehend the risks that are involved. (Kassicieh et al., 2015).

There is ongoing tension within the realm of cyber security between satisfying the requirements of security and satisfying the needs of humans. This tension is caused by the fact that satisfying both sets of requirements can be difficult. In 2020, across the globe the average cost of a data breach was expected to be 3.86 million United States dollars, while the average cost in the United States is expected to be 8.64 million United States dollars. These costs consist of the expenses incurred in identifying and responding to the breach. In addition to the cost of downtime and lost revenue, and the long-term reputational damage incurred by a business and its brand resulting from the breach. All of these costs are incurred as a direct result of the breach (IBM, 2023). The global cyber threat landscape morphs quickly, with increasing data breaches occurring annually. According to a report published by RiskBased Security, an astounding 7.9 billion records have been compromised in the first three quarters of 2019 due to data breaches. This number is more than 110% higher than the number of records compromised during the same period in 2018. The magnitude of the cyber threat

is expected to grow, which has naturally led to an increase in the amount of money spent worldwide on various cybersecurity solutions. Spending on cybersecurity is expected to reach \$188.3 billion in 2023 and then surpass \$260 billion globally by 2026, according to Gartner's predictions. In response to the growing cyber threat, governments worldwide have developed guidelines to assist organizations in implementing effective cyber-security practices. The guidelines developed were in response to the rise of the cyber threat. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in the United States has developed a framework for protecting digital information. The framework recommends continuous and real-time monitoring of all electronic resources to prevent the spread of malicious code and assist in its early detection (CISA News, 2023).

2.1.5 Cyber Threat

Threats to computer systems, networks, and digital devices are cyber threats. In the current digital era, these threats are more prevalent than ever and can harm people, companies, and governments. Malware, phishing, DoS, ransomware, and social engineering attacks are various cyber threats. On social media sites, people have frequently had their photos and personal data stolen by unauthorized users. For instance, Facebook users may be able to view and save pictures and other content from a person's profile, depending on their privacy settings. Social media threats frequently occur in this manner, as imposters use other people's information as their own. Recently, social networks have drawn thousands of users who could become targets of the following kinds of attackers (Maslennikov & Yampolskiy, 2008).

A social network is typically a social structure of individuals or groups connected by at least one specific type of interdependency, such as fellowship. Social networks have attracted many users recently who communicate with potential victims and attackers. Start with phishers and spammers who use social networks to send fraudulent messages to their victims' "friends," cybercriminals and fraudsters who use these same networks to obtain their victims' personal information, finishing their social-engineering assaults, and terrorist organizations and sexual stalkers who create online communities to disseminate their ideas, get publicity for their causes, gaining followers, and increasing membership. There are two categories of cyber threats that clients may encounter.

In Malaysia, national-level cyber safety awareness campaigns have been implemented through governmental agencies, corporate sectors, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) such as the Ministry of Women, Family, and Community Development (MWFCD), the Malaysian Communications and Multimedia Commission (MCMC), Cyber Security Malaysia (CSM), and Digi Telecommunication Sdn. Bhd. (Digi). As provided by the government, the medium is essential

to raise awareness significantly among the target groups, especially students and parents (AHMAD et al., n.d.).

Individuals and organizations must take precautions to secure their computer systems, networks, and digital devices to guard against cyber threats. Implementing firewalls, using antivirus software, updating software with security patches, creating strong passwords, and exercising caution in opening emails, or clicking on links from unknown sources are some security measures that can be taken. Organizations should create and implement cybersecurity policies and procedures to safeguard against cyber threats and train cybersecurity staff members to encourage awareness and best practices.

2.2 Victimization

2.2.1 Types of cybercrime

According to the data kept by the National Crime Records Bureau in India, the total number of cybercrimes committed in India in 2016 amounted to 12,317. However, the numbers were expected to increase to 50,035 by 2020. The highest number of fraud cases were reported in Karnataka (9680). Personal retribution (1,463), anger (814), fraud (30,075), extortion (2411), causing a dispute (1673), playing a prank (252), sexual exploitation (3249), political motivations (355), terrorist activities (109), terrorist recruitment (7), hate crime against the country (163), disrupting public service (90), selling and buying illegal drugs (21), developing one's own business (203), spreading piracy (75), and stealing information (62). Cybercrime has become a primary concern for governments and individuals, as it can cause significant financial and reputational damage. With the increased reliance on technology, it is crucial to take measures to prevent cybercrime and protect sensitive information. It refers to any criminal activity involving computers or the Internet (NCRB, n.d.).

Identity theft happens when criminals use a victim's data to carry out their crimes. A criminal uses this stolen information to assume the victim's identity and engages in several fraudulent activities in their name. Identity theft is a sophisticated cyberattack tactic used by cybercriminals, who also use malware, phishing, and social engineering. Rudimentary methods like mail theft, dumpster diving, and overhearing phone conversations in public places can also lead to identity theft. The ultimate objective of many cyberattacks is to obtain sufficient information about a victim to assume their identity and engage in fraud. Unfortunately, most people fail to realize they have been the victims

of identity theft until they try to open a bank account, apply for a job, apply for a loan, get a collection call, or ask for a new credit card (Fortora, 2023).

Another type of cybercrime is hacking, which involves unauthorized or unpermitted access to or control over the computer network and security systems for improper or illegal purposes. It is the willful and intentional intrusion into a computer program without the owner's consent. It impacts an entity's entire range of information and communication technologies. These include social media scams, threats via the web, communications, and email, data breaches, compromises of the cloud and data storage, and serious data breaches. Hackers only aim to steal private information, embezzle money, disrupt business operations, etc. (iPleaders, 2021).

Phishing is a type of cybercrime in which, a target or targets are contacted through email, phone call, or text message by a con artist pretending to be a representative of a reliable organization in order to trick people into giving up sensitive information like passwords, banking and credit card information, and personally identifiable information (KnowBe4, n.d.). The Information Technology Act of 2000 of India makes penal provisions under Chapter XI of the Act. Further, Section 81 of the IT Act, 2000, contains a non-obstante clause, i.e., "the provisions of this Act shall have a withstanding effect notwithstanding anything inconsistent in addition to that contained in any other law for the time being enforced." The said non-obstante clause gives an overriding effect to the provisions of the IT Act over the other Acts, including the Indian Penal Code. The aforesaid penal provisions of the IT Act, 2000, which are attracted to the phishing scam, have, however, been made bailable under Section 77B of the IT Act intentionally since there is always an identity conflict as to the correct or accurate identity of the person behind the alleged phishing scam. There is always a smokescreen behind the alleged crime as to the identity of the person who has, via these online computer resources, committed the offense, and given the possible misuse of the penal provision for cyber offense as contained in the IT Act, the offense is made bailable (Phishing & Cybersquatting, n.d.). These are examples of the various types of cybercrimes today. As technology advances, new forms of cybercrime may emerge, making it essential for individuals and organizations to stay vigilant and take steps to protect themselves against cyber threats.

2.2.2 Cyber Victimization

Cyber victimization targets an individual using negative behaviors in a cyber context due to adolescent aggression and electronic cooperation (Hinduja & Patchin, 2008). The term "cyber victimization" can also refer to the potentially negative and upsetting experiences that individuals

can have as a direct result of their actions while using the Internet. The actions of the individuals themselves can cause these experiences. This can encompass various harmful online behaviors, including cyberbullying, cyberstalking, harassment, and other inappropriate conduct.

People who are harassed or bullied online are at risk of experiencing severe consequences, some of which may include adverse effects on their mental health, estrangement from their social circle, and even, in some cases, physical harm (Eroglu et al., 2022). Because of the changes in their bodies, the dynamics of their social relationships, and the intensity of their feelings, people often become more vulnerable to the repercussions of being bullied during their teenage years. Particularly, the physical changes that occur with the onset of adolescence, the status of individuals within groups at school, the quality of friendship relationships, and the availability of peer support are all factors associated with cyber victimization experiences (Villora et al., 2020). Additionally, studies demonstrate that online peer victimization typically follows unfavorable behavior events like addictive behaviors, emotional distress, and interpersonal stress (Sun et al., 2019).

Cyber bystanders' responses may also be a factor in the rise in cyberbullying behavior because they help cyberbullies achieve their objectives of dominance, popularity, and power among their peers (Runions et al., 2013). As technological development continues, new forms of cybercrime will likely exist. Consequently, individuals and organizations must maintain vigilance and take active measures to safeguard themselves against the dangers posed by cyberattacks. While incidents of traditional cyberbullying, such as name-calling and spreading rumors, are still at an all-time high, an increasing number of parents are reporting racially motivated cyberbullying, according to the "McAfee Connected Family Report," published by a software company. The survey results based on the responses of parent found that more than one in four children (28%) worldwide have been the target of racially motivated cyberbullying. It has been estimated that the rate of cyberbullying for racially motivated reasons is 34% in the United States and 42% in India, respectively. This danger is most pronounced in the United States and India. In the meantime, some nations, such as the United Kingdom (19%), France (17%), Japan (16%), and Mexico (14%), report rates that are significantly lower than the average (McAfee, 2022).

Technology is the common denominator in the behavior pattern that is referred to as cyberstalking. A cyberstalker is called a person who commits criminal acts through electronic communication, social media, and other technology forms. However, a review of recent cases reveals that individuals who engage in cyberstalking frequently steal identities and engage in other illegal activities. The circumstances that surround each instance of cyberstalking are also unique. Using

insulting names is one aspect of cyberbullying that has not evolved much. Name-calling is the most common form of cyberbullying that children experience. It has a prevalence rate of 40% worldwide and is experienced by 56% of children in the United Kingdom and 50% in the United States. The global prevalence rate of this form of cyberbullying is 40%. Despite the generally low reported rates of cyberbullying in Japan, this percentage is high across the board, including at 23% in Japan.

However, a lack of communication is the second most common form, with exclusion from group chats and conversations accounting for 36% of cases worldwide and reaching as high as 49% in Australia and 43% in the United Kingdom and Mexico, respectively. Being physically separated from one's social circle is the most extreme form of social isolation. Considering that every other nation reported a rate of at least 30%, Japan's rate of 13% once again stands out as an anomaly compared to the rest of the world. The spreading of untrue rumors is the third most common type of cyberbullying, and it has been experienced by 28% of children worldwide. Japan stands out as having the highest percentage of reported cyberbullying, with 44%. This is followed by Germany, which has 35%, and India, which has 39% (McAfee, 2022).

2.2.3 Vulnerable Population

The term "vulnerable population" refers to a group of individuals who are at an increased risk of being harmed or disadvantaged compared to the general population. Cyberbullying motivated by racism affects children as young as ten years old, according to reports from 22% of those children. Parents in India report that cyberbullying affects their children at a rate of 45% for boys aged 10 to 14 and 41% for girls in the same age range. Girls aged 17 to 18 years old make up another vulnerable group of children, accounting for 42% of cases in the United States; boys aged 15 to 16 years old account for 33% of cases in Germany; and boys aged 17 to 18 years old account for 42% of cases in Brazil. It is concerning that children in Canada between the age group of 10 and 14 were twice as likely as their older counterparts, to report experiencing racism online. This may result from several factors, such as the individual's age, gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, disabilities, or health conditions, as well as any other factors that may limit their access to resources and support systems. Boys, in the ages of 10 and 14 years in India, boys between the ages of 17 and 18 years in the United States, and girls in 15 and 16 years of age in Australia reported the highest rates of receiving physical threats. In the meantime, young boys and girls between 10 and 14 years in the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Japan, Brazil, and Mexico reported feeling the safest despite having percentages in the single digits. One child out of every six has reported receiving explicit images or messages due to being the target of sexual harassment via the Internet, which is

another severe form of cyberbullying. India, with a rate of 30%, and the United States, with a rate of 19%, both lead the pack of countries with the highest rates of sexual harassment, while Canada and Mexico both have rates of 14% (McAfee, 2022).

Open lines of communication within the family have been found to strengthen the child-parent bond, which is a deterrent to online bullying (S et al., 2017). The developmental stage known as adolescence is a time that is particularly predisposed to the onset of issues related to psychological well-being and mental health. One of these issues, psychological distress, can be defined as the expression of unpleasant feelings and emotions during symptoms of anxiety and depression, which typically results in impaired psychological functioning at the behavioural, cognitive, and emotional levels (Benzi et al., 2022). When it comes to problematic online behaviors and cyberbullying, previous studies have indicated that gender is also a relevant variable to take into consideration. This is the case in terms of gender. Therefore, girls are more likely to use social networking sites, which allow them to communicate with their contemporaries (Kuss et al., 2014). Conversely, boys spend more time engaging in activities like playing video games or visiting websites (Tafur-Mendoza et al., 2020). On the other hand, the findings are not definitive regarding cyberbullying. According to the findings of some studies, girls are more likely to be victimized of cyberbullying. Others claim that boys are more likely to be both cyber-attackers and victims than girls (Lattanner & Schroeder, 2014; Kuss et al., 2014). Despite this, others found no variations (Center UBA et al., n.d.).

2.2.4 Cyberbullies Motives

There are various motivations for people who engage in intimidating and harassing behavior online, and these reasons can change depending on the context in which the behavior occurs. The common motivations for cyberbullying are the desire for power and control, vengeance or retaliation, attention-seeking, jealousy or envy, prejudice or discrimination, boredom, or a lack of empathy. A form of traumatized and repeated power play, bullying consists of unprovoked teasing and, in certain circumstances, abuse by one or more children to hurt, cause pain, and distress another child. Bullying is a form of traumatizing and repeated power play that involves unprovoked teasing. This technology provides everything a bully would look for if they were looking for it. It provides the perpetrator with an ideal channel through which they can traumatize their victim without fearing repercussions. Anonymity, slow response times for telecommunications services, and weak laws are benefits that the bully can take advantage of. The use of traditional and conventional forms of bullying, such as cyberbullying through mobile phones, is a tactic adolescents utilize to amplify their dominant position. According to a study conducted by Abeele and Cock, RD, it was

discovered that girls are more likely than boys to engage in gossip through SMS. The same study also discovered that sending rumors via text message was the most common form of cyberbullying that could be carried out using mobile phones (Venkataraghavan, 2015).

This highlights the need for parents and educators to educate children on the responsible use of mobile phones and social media and monitor their online behavior to prevent cyberbullying. Additionally, individuals must be aware of the potential harm gossiping can cause and strive to promote positivity and kindness in their interactions.

2.2.5 The social psychology of Cyberbullying

It is often believed that traditional and online bullying occurs between a bully (aggressor) and a bullied person (victim). However, the situation is more complex, so we need an ecological model to understand this phenomenon well (D.L. & S.M., 2004). It is primarily a group phenomenon rather than an individual one. It always occurs in a sociocultural context, so examining the role of the family, school, and community is crucial. Social psychology has a great deal to say about the fields of bullying and cyberbullying, as both phenomena always take place in a particular psychosocial context, to the extent that to properly understand them, we need to analyze the cultural, social community, family, school, and group contexts (Bernal et al., 2013). Hence, many social and psychological themes are most attractive to help understand cyberbullying. These themes include those related to the group, family, aggressive conduct, gender, attitudes, communication processes, help-seeking behavior, values, moral disengagement, psychosocial needs, or power over the situation. Cyberbullying is related to other forms of violent and aggressive conduct (E et al., 2010), (Park et al., 2014). So, applying cyberbullying to existing models of violent conduct is most useful (Fernández Villanueva, 2011), particularly in matters such as power over the situation (Díaz, 2009) or inhibitory effects caused by empathy (Castillo et al., 2013), (Gini et al., 2007). The potential bully's concept of right and wrong will also influence (Fuchs et al., 2009) as it will facilitate or hinder moral disengagement (Bandura, 1999). A clear association between antisocial behavior and low levels of empathy (Jolliffe & Farrington, 2004). Nevertheless, it has been indicated that antisocial behavior in bullying is associated only with affective empathy (Caravita et al., 2009) and not with cognitive empathy (Shariff, 2013), unlike in cyberbullying, where it is associated with both types of empathy (Baroncelli & Ciucci, 2014). Walrave and Heirman (Walrave & Heirman, 2010) indicated that individuals who engage in cyberbullying also tend to minimize the effects their conduct has on victims. There have been very few studies into the moral aspects of cyberbullying are available (Talwar et al., 2014). Very little is known about adolescents' moral evaluations of cyberbullying situations. Bullies themselves often morally justify bullying (Burton et

al., 2012), and when people's moral principles are not consistent with their conduct, they use moral disengagement as a mediator between both aspects, which thus legitimizes immoral conduct (Bandura, 2002). Therefore, people who participate in cases of cyberbullying feel less guilty than those who take part in traditional bullying (Christian Elledge et al., 2013). Because of the ease with which they can disengage morally the effect that their behavior has on victims is not seen (Pettalia et al., 2013). Indeed, merely knowing that the teacher can intervene reduces cyberbullying behavior (Christian Elledge et al., 2013).

2.2.6 Effects on Victims

Cyberbullying can have serious adverse effects on the victims, both in the short-term and long-term. It can cause significant psychological distress in victims, including anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, and suicidal ideation. Recent national attention to several cases of suicide among youth victims of cyberbullying (Køhlert, 2015). Concerns about its prevalence and psychological impact have been raised. Most states now have legislation that requires schools to address electronic harassment in their antibullying policies (Patchin & Hinduja, 2010). However, schools lack information about cyberbullying's correlates and consequences and how they may differ from those of school bullying. To inform the schools' efforts, research is needed to examine the overlap between cyberbullying and school bullying and identify which youths are targeted with either or both types of bullying. It is also necessary to understand whether the psychological correlates of cyberbullying are similar to those of school bullying and whether students targeted by both forms of bullying are at increased risk of psychological harm.

With reports indicating that 93% of teens are active Internet users and 75% own a cell phone, up from 45% in 2004 (A et al., 2010), there is an excellent potential for cyberbullying among youths. However, the extent of cyberbullying victimization and its prevalence relative to school bullying is unclear. Studies have found that anywhere from 9% to 40% of students are victims of cyberbullying (Ferdon C & M. F., 2009). It is suggested that online victimization is less prevalent than school bullying and other forms of offline victimization (Wang et al., 2009). A few reports provide information on youths' involvement in bullying online and on school property. Cyberbullying victims may avoid going to work or school and withdraw from social interactions, which can cause social isolation and loneliness. Physical health issues like headaches, stomachaches, and sleep disturbances can also result from cyberbullying. Due to increased stress and distraction, cyberbullying victims may perform worse in school or on the job. Cyberbullying may make relationships with family and friends strained or even fall apart. Cyberbullying victims who

experience it severely may experience PTSD, which can cause flashbacks, nightmares, and other symptoms. Early recognition and treatment of PTSD may alter adolescents' trajectory toward future physical and cyberviolence, behavioral disorders, and social consequences (Cohen et al., 2008). Regulatory agencies are increasingly urging standardized evaluation and treatment of PTSD, particularly for high-risk adolescents presenting for clinical care (Cohen et al., 2010).

2.2.7 Indian Studies on Cyberbullying

Given the paucity of research of this kind in low-resource countries like India, the current study sought to investigate the longitudinal relationship between being a victim of cyberbullying and experiencing depression, as well as having thoughts about ending one's own life, among adolescents and young adults. The surveys "Understanding the Lives of Adolescents and Young Adults" (UDAYA-2015-16 and 2018-19) were carried out in Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, India's two most populous states. The data used in this study were taken from those surveys to accomplish the study's goals. Bivariate and logistic regression analysis were conducted using a sample of 4428 male and 11,864 female adolescents (aged 10–19 years) from separate cohorts, respectively. Over three years, the percentage of female respondents who reported being victims of cyberbullying increased from 3.8% to 6.4%, while the percentage of male respondents who reported being victims increased from 1.9% to 5.6%. When people were in their early 20s, the prevalence of depressive symptoms was approximately 33% among females and 16.6% among males. When compared to males, nearly 7.5% of females have reported having serious thoughts about attempting suicide in the previous year, whereas only 2.3% of males have done so. Those adolescents who were the targets of cyberbullying were found to have a 2.07 higher risk of having depressive symptoms than those who were not the targets of cyberbullying.

Similarly, research has shown that adolescents who have been the target of cyberbullying are 2.50 times more likely to harbor suicidal thoughts than their peers who have not been the target of cyberbullying. According to the findings, victims of cyberbullying led to an increased risk of experiencing depressive symptoms and having thoughts of suicide. These negative effects continue for more extended periods. Therefore, cyberbullying and related mental health issues must be addressed with more effective strategies, such as increased awareness of the nuances of online harassment among adolescents and young adults. This is particularly important in countries where cyber bullying is prevalent (Maurya et al., 2022).

The potential moderating effect of gender was investigated in a longitudinal study involving adolescents from China, Cyprus, India, and the United States. The relationships between Machiavellianism, popularity goals, and cyberbullying involvement (i.e., victimization, perpetration) were examined. The study looked at both victimization and perpetration. This study involved 2,452 young people ages 13 to 16 from China, Cyprus, India, and the United States. Approximately 49.1% of the participants were female. During the fall of 2014, they conducted surveys on aspects of Machiavellianism, popularity goals, and cyberbullying victimization and perpetration. A year later, in 2015, adolescents participated in surveys regarding their experiences as victims or perpetrators of cyberbullying. According to the findings, Machiavellianism and popularity goals were positively associated with Time 2 cyberbullying victimization and perpetration for all adolescents. Machiavellianism was also positively associated with Time 1 cyberbullying victimization and perpetration. The correlations between Machiavellianism and cyberbullying perpetration and between popularity goals and cyberbullying perpetration were found to be more vital for boys of Chinese and Indian descent than for girls. It was discovered that adolescents in the United States exhibit opposite patterns regarding their popularity goals and involvement in Time 2 cyberbullying. There was no indication that gender played a role in developing any associations for adolescents in Cyprus or for the victimization of cyberbullying in Time 2. The social-ecological perspective helps gain an understanding of how bullying is influenced by the many different contexts in which it occurs (Wright et al., 2022)

2.3 Cyber usage and Victimization

2.3.1 Country-specific and age-specific research

In today's world, there are 5.16 billion people have access Internet, access which means that 64.4% of the world's total population is now online, as stated in the report Digital Overview 2023. The data shows a 1.9% increase in internet users worldwide over the past year. However, because of delays in data reporting, the actual growth is likely to be higher than this figure suggests. There are currently 4.76 billion people using social media platforms across the globe, equivalent to just under 60% of the world's total population. However, social media user numbers have slowed significantly over the past few months, with this year's net addition of 137 million new users equivalent to an annual growth rate of just 3%. According to the same study, 94% and 94.6% of internet users between the ages of 16 and 64 participate in using chat, messenger, or social networking sites. The data provided by GWI also demonstrates that people are spending more time using social media platforms. An average person using the Internet and is of working age now spends more than two

and a half hours per day using social media platforms, according to the company's most recent round of research. This is the highest figure we have seen so far. Activities related to social media now account for almost four minutes out of every ten minutes spent online, making this the first time in history that social media has represented such a significant proportion of total time spent online. When compared, these statistics demonstrate that the average person who uses the Internet and is of working age now spends 30% more time each day on social media than they do watch "traditional" television (i.e., broadcast and cable TV channels) (Global Digital Insights, 2023).

According to the internet crime records maintained by the FBI, the number of reported cybercrime incidents increased to 800,944 in 2022, indicating that a minimum of 422 million people were affected by the crimes committed online. In 2023, there will be breaches in nearly 33 billion accounts, and the total cost is projected to be \$8 trillion. It is estimated that 2,328 illegal activities take place online every single day. At least 6.5 million people have been victims of cybercrime over the past 21 years, from 2001 to 2021, with an estimated loss of nearly \$26 billion during the same period (James, 2022). People of all ages and genders are creating profiles on online social networks to connect in this digital world. The number of people signing up for these profiles continues to rise. Some users have dozens, hundreds, or thousands of friends and followers across their various profiles.

Nevertheless, there is a rise in the number of fake profiles. Fake profiles that post inappropriate or illegal content frequently spam users with legitimate accounts. In addition, fake profiles can be created by misrepresenting a known individual in order to harass that individual. Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and LinkedIn are the websites and apps that are most frequently targeted when creating "fake profiles." (Cyber Crime Cell, n.d.).

2.3.2 Gender Differences in Cyberbullying

The findings obtained from research on gender differences in traditional bullying served as a jumping-off point for research on gender differences in cyberbullying. Research shows that boys are more likely to engage in direct physical or verbal aggression than girls. This holds true regardless of the specific form of aggression in question (Griezel et al., 2012). It has been reported that girls are more likely to engage in indirect forms of aggression. This type of aggression involves the victim being excluded from the peer group or having his or her personal and social reputation questioned. These findings support the hypothesis that direct aggression is more characteristic of people of the male gender, whereas indirect aggression is more characteristic of people of the female gender. This

division between more masculine and feminine forms of aggression has been attributed to several different factors, including biological reasons (for example, girls have less strength physically), interpersonal reasons (for example, the social structure of groups of girls, as these groups are smaller and more intimate when compared with groups of boys), which would make indirect aggression a more effective strategy. There are also gender socialization factors, such as adults being less tolerant of girls getting involved in physical aggression, which would mean that girls would have to adopt subtler and less visible forms of aggressive behavior. (Kistner et al., 2010). These justifications, along with the findings of numerous studies, have led to a great deal of general agreement regarding girls' use of more submissive aggression in the context of traditional bullying (Kowalski et al., 2014). This places them squarely at the center of attention when it comes to investigations into the extent to which cyberbullying occurs. This starting point is unsurprising when we consider that cyberbullying has been described as psychological and emotional abuse carried out through slander or spreading information on the Internet, and where the perpetrator attacks the victims' privacy and intimacy but remains anonymous. (Beran & Li, 2008). Because indirect cyberbullying shares many of the same characteristics as traditional indirect bullying, preliminary research on cyberbullying assumed that girls were implied to the same extent or even a greater extent than boys were. On the other hand, there has not always been access to evidence in the real world to back up this premise. Research has provided information that is quite contradictory, indicating that a clear gender pattern in terms of being involved as aggressors or victims has not been found. Some researchers have found, in general, that boys are more likely to be aggressors than girls. Others have found that the girls are more likely to be victims than boys (Walrave & Heirman, 2010). Other studies have reported that boys act more aggressively but found no significant differences in victimization. Other studies have indicated that girls act more as both aggressors and victims than boys (Mark & Ratliffe, 2011) or that boys act more as aggressors and victims (Festl & Quandt, 2012). Numerous studies have not found gender differences between victims and aggressors (Griezel et al., 2012). Other research has suggested that gender differences depend on the analyzed forms of cyberbullying (Monks et al., 2012). As a result, when formulating strategies for the prevention and treatment of cyberbullying, it is essential to consider the nuances of gender differences in the phenomenon. It is also vital to address the issue of cyberbullying as a whole, regardless of gender, to ensure that everyone can participate in online activities in a safe and respectful atmosphere.

2.3.3 Prevalence of Cyberbullying among college students

Students in higher education institutions are not immune to cyberbullying; they may be especially susceptible to being harassed and abused online. Students in higher education frequently use various social media platforms, which can make them more vulnerable to being bullied online. People between 18 and 22 years and those enrolled in college are "one of the heaviest users" of social media. The most commonly used media types by billions of people is Social media (Wang et al., 2015). The current generation of college-aged students is the first one to grow up with social media, according to this study, which notes this fact. These students are active on various social media platforms, including LinkedIn, Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram, and Twitter. Some students may experience pressure due to the social dynamics of college, leading them to engage in harmful online behavior such as cyberbullying. The young adults with the growing use of social media, makes it easier for them to compare themselves with others, which can result in poor mental health and dissatisfaction with life (Soohinda et al., 2021). According to a few studies, individuals who use social media may experience an increased risk of developing social anxiety. A study carried out in Kolkata concluded that reliance on social networking sites (SNSs) and feelings of anxiety and depression/ There was a significant association with one another among medical students (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2018). Many students experience increased anxiety during their time in college, making them more susceptible to the damaging effects of cyberbullying. On some college campuses, there may be a culture of hazing or bullying, and this behavior can sometimes be carried over to online platforms. It is possible that active use of social media could reduce social anxiety by positively mediating communication capacity and that improved communication capacity could reduce the contribution that passive use of social media makes to social anxiety. Educators need to pay attention to the varying ways different forms of social media use can affect levels of social anxiety. College students who improve their ability to communicate with one another may experience less social anxiety (Lai et al., 2023). Harassment and bullying can occur online if students compete for grades and other academic achievements. Students in higher education can experience significant adverse effects due to cyberbullying, including feelings of anxiety, depression, social isolation, and even difficulties in their academic or professional lives. It is essential for educational institutions like colleges and universities to take preventative measures against cyberbullying and to offer support and resources to students who are victims of this form of harassment online.

2.3.4 Need for the Study

The COVID-19-induced lockdown caused most Indians to increase internet usage, contributing to the anticipated rise in cybercrimes. People were cut off from one another in-person due to the pandemic, Individuals have also been actively posting new accomplishments they achieved during the pandemic-induced lockdown and expressing their opinions more vocally than in the past. Social media had become most individuals' only communication mode. In addition, individuals have been actively posting new accomplishments they achieved during the lockdown. When people consume more content online and have most of their social and professional interactions on these online mediums, regulating the activity is of the utmost importance. People are more susceptible and vulnerable to comments and acts of hate online. People were more susceptible to the wrongdoings of their tormentors. In these circumstances, neither the bully nor the victim is aware of the repercussions or the dangers that their online actions may pose (Ozden & Icelliglu, 2014). Similar to the negative effects of traditional bullying, victims of cyberbullying frequently experience feelings of rage, helplessness, fear, and sadness. These emotions are consistent with the effects of traditional bullying. Because of the additional challenge posed by the anonymity afforded by the Internet, victims of cyberbullying frequently report feeling helpless because they are unsure how to end the behavior (Hoff & Mitchell, 2009).

According to the findings of a study, 20% of the youth population surveyed participated in some form of cyberbullying, either as a victim, a bully, or both. The study revealed that younger students who faced this were, those who spent more time playing games on weekdays. While being more confident in cyberspace and actively using mobile phones, they were more likely to be involved in cyberbullying than other students. This was shown to be the case regardless of whether or not the students were confident in their ability to navigate cyberspace (Shin & Ahn, 2015).

According to another study, students from sexual minorities, and those who text at least 50 times per day were more likely to being victims of cyberbullying (Rice et al., 2015). It was discovered that Facebook and text messaging are the most common forms of cyberbullying. Individuals with disabilities were found to be another factor that had a high impact on the likelihood of someone becoming a victim of cyberbullying (Kowalski et al., 2016). Social influence was found to significantly impact a person's cyberbullying behavior and intention (Lee & Wu, 2018). According to additional research, inherent factors like social media use and online activity can amplify harmful behaviors like cyberbullying, cyber harassment, and cyberstalking (Al-Rahmi et al., 2019). As a result, following the pandemic, several people who use social media have reported that the time

spent on these social media platforms has increased. The percentage of SME elders was found to be higher among the females than the males, as well as among younger people in comparison to older people. Higher SME was found to be positively associated with the prevalence of mental health problems, which were found to be highly associated with cyberbullying activity. As a result, it could have led to increased activity in cyberbullying, as mental health problems were found to be highly associated with cyberbullying (Gao et al., 2020).

Chapter 3

Rational of the Study

Victims of cyberbullying often experience feelings of anger, powerlessness, fear, and sadness, which are consistent with the negative effects of traditional bullying. With the added problem of anonymity in cyberbullying, victims tend to feel helpless as they are unaware of how to stop such acts (Hoff & Mitchell, 2009). A study showed that 20% of the youth population surveyed was involved in cyberbullying as a victim, a bully, or both. The study further showed that younger students who spent more time playing games on weekdays while being more confident in cyberspace and active in using mobile phones were more likely to be involved in cyberbullying than other students (Shin & Ahn, 2015).

Yet another study revealed that Facebook and text messaging were the most frequent mediums for cyberbullying. Sexual minority students and students who texted at least 50 times daily were likelier to report cyberbullying victimization (Rice et al., 2015). Another factor that was found to have high outcomes for cyberbullying victimization was individuals with disabilities (Kowalski et al., 2016). Social influence was found to significantly impact a person's cyberbullying behavior and intention (Lee & Wu, 2018).

Further findings also suggested that inherent factors like social media usage and cyber engagement amplify detrimental acts like cyberbullying, cyber harassment, and cyberstalking (Al-Rahmi et al., 2019). Many social media users have observed a spike in the time spent on social media due to the pandemic (Gao et al., 2020).

Chapter 4

Methodology

4.1 Problem and objective

According to various studies done in different countries there is increase in cyber victimization with the increase use of social media among students (12-18 years) . This study aims to find the relationship between the two variables in the Indian context.

4.2. Hypothesis

H₁: There is a correlation between social network usage and cyber victimisation

H₀: There is no correlation between social network usage and cyber victimisation.

4.3. Operational definitions

Social networking refers to the online space students use to connect, share, communicate, establish, or maintain a connection with others for academic, entertainment, socialization, etc. (Savita Gupta, 2018). It refers to the activities and behaviors of individuals on social networking platforms. Social networking platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Snapchat, have become integral to people's lives in recent years. Cyber victimization is how others are victimized through information and communication technologies. It refers to the experience of being targeted and victimized through online platforms or digital communication channels. It encompasses various forms of online harassment, abuse, and bullying that can have detrimental effects on individuals.

4.4. Sample

The sample for survey were individuals in the age group of 12 to 18 years. Both male and female, were eligible to participate in the study. The individuals should have been actively using at least one social media account (Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, Twitter, etc.) and use one messenger application (WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Telegram, Viber, etc.) that they are actively engaged in. The individuals were students and residents of India.

Google Forms was prepared and the questionnaire link was distributed via email and WhatsApp until 100 individuals responded. Convenient sampling technique and snowball method was employed.

4.5 Research Design

The study aimed to understand the relationship between two variables (social media usage and cyber-victimization). A correlational research design was used. Correlational research design is advantageous when it is not possible or ethical to manipulate variables. Correlation research design allows researchers to examine the association between variables and identify patterns or trends. Additionally, it provides valuable insights into complex phenomena and inform future research.

4.6 Tests and Tools

4.6.1 The Social Networking Usage Questionnaire (TSNUQ)

The Social Networking Usage Questionnaire measures social media usage—academic, entertainment, and socialization—in online spaces. The scale has 19 self-reported items rated on the 5-point Likert-type scale from 1 (never) to 5 (always). The social networking questionnaire was developed to understand the purposes of social networking usage by students in an Indian context (Savita Gupta, 2018). Academic usage questions are irrelevant to our study; hence, they will be removed from the questionnaire (Holly Reid1 et al., 2021). (Refer to Appendix A)

4.6.2 Adolescent Cyber-Victimization Scale (CYBVICS)

CYBVICS is an adaptation of the Adolescent Victimization through Mobile Phone and Internet Scale (Sofía Buelga, 2019). The new scale is an updated version. With the use of the smartphones, the distinction between the cell phone and the Internet currently makes no sense. Moreover, this new scale includes eight other items, on the original scale. Thus, the Cyber-Victimization Scale consisted of 18 self-reported items on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranges from 1 (never) to 5 (always) were rated. The adolescents' experience as a victim of cyberbullying in the last 12 months are measured on this scale. A self-report measure was adopted because of its capacity to recognize adolescents' cyber-victim behaviors. (Refer to Appendix B)

4.7 Data Analysis Techniques

The Pearson correlation coefficient, a descriptive statistic, was determined to measure the magnitude and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables—social media use and cyber victimization. Interpretations were made with a significance level of $p=0.05$.

4.8 Ethical Determination of the Study

Consent to participate in the survey was obtained from the individuals. Those agreed to participate voluntarily in the study were informed about the aim and application of the study. (Refer to Appendix C)

4.9 Statistical Analysis

SPSS (The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences-PC) program was used to analyze the data statistically. The Mean and Standard Deviation were calculated. The Pearson correlation coefficient, a descriptive statistic, used to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables—social media use and cyber victimization. Interpretations were made with a significance level of $p=0.05$.

Chapter 5

Results and Discussion

The focus of the research study is to examine the hypothesis that social media use is correlated with cyberbullying. There is a correlation seen between social media use and increased cyber victimization. Due to the anonymity and ease of use, social media have become breeding grounds for bullying and harassment. It must be remembered that being a victim of online crime is not an inevitable consequence of using social media. Instead, it is people who intend harm to others who abuse these sites.

5.1 Table 1 Demographic Table

	Frequency (<i>n</i>)	Percentage
Gender		
Male	37	37%
Female	63	63%
Others	0	0%
Age		
12	4	4%
13	4	4%
14	8	8%
15	9	9%
16	14	14%
17	20	20%
18	41	41%
Education Level		
7th Standard	4	4%
8th Standard	3	3%
9th Standard	4	4%
10 th Standard	18	18%

11 th Standard	10	10%
12 th Standard	31	31%
1 st Year Graduation	6	6%
2 th Year Graduation	24	24%
Social Media		
Facebook	26	26%
Instagram	74	74%
Twitter	14	14%
Snapchat	40	40%
WhatsApp	85	85%
Telegram	15	15%
Discord	3	3%
LinkedIn	2	2%
BeReal	1	1%
YouTube	5	5%
Tumblr	1	1%
Reddit	2	2%
Discovery Baby	1	1%
Pinterest	1	1%
Type of family		
Nuclear Family	65	65%
Joint Family	24	24%
Single Parent Family	5	5%
Step Family	1	1%
Grandparents Family	5	5%
Individuals working in the family		
Both Parents Working	43	43%

Only Father Working	47	47%
Only Mother Working	6	6%
I am working	10	10%
Sibling Working	14	14%

Note Demographic Table, Total number of participants $N = 100$

The following table presents the demographic information that was gathered throughout the course of the study. This data facilitates a more profound comprehension of the populace, specifically in terms of the origin of individuals and the potential influence of demographic factors on their behaviours.

Figure 1 Age

Note: Age of the participants

The following bar chart depicts the age distribution of the study participants. The study's sample size consisted of 100 participants, with an average age of 16.49. Individuals aged 18 to 22 and those currently pursuing higher education are among the most frequent consumers of social media. The present cohort of university students represents the initial generation to have been raised alongside social media (Wang et al., 2015). The students exhibit a high level of engagement on diverse social media channels, such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Snapchat, Instagram, and Twitter (Soohinda et al., 2021)

Figure 2 Social Media

Note: Social Media used by the participants

The following bar graph depicts the social media platforms utilized by the participants in the study. Among the sample of 100 participants in the study, the social media platforms that were most frequently utilized by the individuals were WhatsApp (85) and Instagram (74), respectively. In contrast to the study's results, it was discovered that Facebook garnered the greatest amount of traffic, accounting for approximately 58% of social media platform usage in India during July of 2022. (Statista, 2022).

Figure 3 Family Type

Note: Type of family of the participants

The below pie chart represents the family type of the participants in the study. The majority of the individuals i.e., 64% come from nuclear families whereas 24% come from joint family

backgrounds. It also exemplifies the shift from joint families to smaller, more self-sufficient units. There is a total of 6 individuals who have scored averagely high on the cyber victimization scale 3 of them come from a nuclear family. This result indicates that the family type might have an effect on victimization.

Figure 4 Working Individuals

Note: Individuals working in the family

The following bar graph depicts the number of individuals employed within the family. The sample size consisted of 47 participants from single-income households and 43 participants from dual-income households. Ten individuals were engaged in self-employment. The available evidence does not provide a definitive indication of any association between familial employment, social media engagement, and the experience of cyber victimization.

Figure 5 Gender

Note: Gender ratio of the individuals participating in the study

Among the sample of 100 participants under investigation, 63% were identified as female while the remaining 37% were identified as male. Among the population under study, a total of 6% of individuals have obtained high scores on both scales. Of this group, 1.85% are male and 0.63% are female. This implies that a greater proportion of males have been subjected to cyberbullying in comparison to females. The "Understanding the Lives of Adolescents and Young Adults" (UDAYA) surveys conducted in 2015-16 and 2018-19 involved a cohort of 4,428 male and 11,864 female adolescents between the ages of 10 and 19 years. During a period of three years, there was an increase in the proportion of male participants who reported experiencing victimization from 1.9% to 5.6%. However, the results are inconclusive with respect to cyberbullying (Maurya et al., 2022).. Based on the results of certain research studies, it has been observed that females exhibit a higher likelihood of experiencing cyberbullying as victims. According to some sources, there is a belief that males exhibit a higher propensity to engage in cyber-attacks and experience victimization through such means compared to females (Lattanner & Schroeder, 2014; Kuss et al., 2014).

5.1 Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Standard Deviation	N
Media Usage	63.85	11.086	100
Cyber V	24.34	10.226	100

Note: Mean and Standard Deviation

5.2 Table 3 Correlation

		Media Usage	Cyber_V
Media Usage	Pearson correlation		.078
	Sig (2 tailed)		.442
	N		100

Note: Pearson 2-tailed correlation

It is observed that a minimum score of 19 and a maximum score of 95 on the social media usage questionnaires (TSNUQ), a mean score of 63.85, and a standard deviation of 11.08, the data indicates social media usage among the age group (12–18 years) is above average.

The minimum score on the Adolescent Cyber Victimization Scale (CYBVICS) is 18, the maximum score is 90, and the mean score is 24.34, with a standard deviation of 10.226. The findings show that although cyber victimization does occur, it is not very severe. The correlation between the two scales is $r = 0.78$ and $P = 0.4$, which is positive, high, greater than 0.05, and insignificant. This indicates that the likelihood of people becoming online victims of crime increases with increased social media use.

The present study, which was conducted on a restricted sample size, has demonstrated an association between the two variables as indicated in Table 1. Nonetheless, the magnitude of the issue will only be discernible upon examination of more substantial figures. A larger sample size may yield findings that provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship

Chapter 6

Conclusion

Social media use has increased cyber victimization, and appropriate social media use and cyber victimization guidelines are needed. Because of these ideas, neoliberal subjects indulge in cyberbullying, lack discipline, and social disengagement. Cyberbullying preys on revered groups, but open family communication strengthens child-parent bonds. Cyberbullying is motivated by power, retaliation, attention-seeking, jealousy, prejudice, and boredom. Cyberbullying is complex and requires an ecological approach. College students using social media are vulnerable to cyberbullying, which may lead to mental illness and misery. Victims of cyberbullying experience fury, powerlessness, fear, and sadness, and socially influence their behaviour and purpose. These facts are evident from the secondary sources of information reviewed in the literature.

It is necessary to research to discover if teenagers subjected to both cyberbullying and school bullying are at a greater risk of psychological harm. Early PTSD diagnosis and therapy aid in the prevention of Victims of cyberbullying is more likely to have sadness and suicidal thoughts, which stay longer.

Smartphones are increasingly popular, yet they pose concerns such as child sex abuse, sexual exploitation, and unauthorized data use. Parents and educators should educate their children about responsible phone and social media use. Colleges and universities must work to prevent cyberbullying and aid victims. Research, partnership with social media corporations, law enforcement, mental health professionals, and social media safety education are required to understand the relationship between social media use and cyber victimization. Organizations and governments have developed mobile phone safety policies and initiatives to decrease risks. Cybersecurity safeguards Internet users from cyber threats, such as identity theft, hacking, malware, phishing, cyberstalking, cyberbullying, denial-of-service attacks, online scams, IP theft, and cyber victimization.

6.1 Implications

This research may assist in gaining a better understanding of the prevalence of the usage of social media platforms as well as cyber victimization in Indian society. This will help schools and

universities establish measures to identify people being bullied in online contexts and assist such individuals. Student counselors will be able to get insights into the behavioral patterns of bullies and create coping mechanisms for those who are bullied. Research findings may be used by governmental organizations such as the Cyber Cell to determine the age groups more susceptible to crime and the types of crimes often perpetrated. By identifying the age groups and types of crimes that are most prevalent, the Cyber Cell can develop targeted prevention strategies and allocate resources more effectively. Additionally, schools and community organizations can use the coping mechanisms developed in this study to better support those who have experienced bullying.

6.2 Delimitation

Adolescents and teenagers between the ages of 12 and 18 years old. There were both male and female participants, as well as other sexes. Each person should have a single social media profile (for example, on Instagram, Facebook, Snapchat, and Twitter) and use a single messaging service (WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, Telegram, Viber, etc.). The individual must be located in India.

6.3 Limitation

There is no personal connection between the participants and which has restricted understanding of the problem. As the data was gathered online, determining its authenticity was difficult. Because the questionnaire was self-reported, participants could provide more socially acceptable responses. The sample size can be large.

6.3 Suggestions for future research

Cybervictimization and social media need more research. This has been studied extensively. Understanding social media cybervictimization mechanisms is crucial. Social media risks must be identified. Age, gender, personality, and social media use are examples. Cybervictimization's short- and long-term effects need further study. Preventing and treating social media cybervictimization requires research. Educating youth and adults, promoting responsible social media use, and improving victim reporting and support are examples. Research is needed to stop social media cyberbullying. Develop algorithms and filters to detect and block abusive content, as well as tools to protect victims and report abuse. More research is needed to understand and prevent cyber victimization from social media use. Social media, law enforcement, and mental health professionals must work together to combat cyberbullying. Social media safety education is vital. To understand how age affects cyberbullying and victimization, the age group and an equal number

of samples will be considered. Gender too. The study is population-representative. Age, gender, and cyberbullying/victimization are better understood. Socioeconomic status and location may help explain cyberbullying. Teens may cyberbully due to life stresses. It's rarely discussed. Social media's negative effects on teens' mental health require this multidisciplinary approach. Clinical and research settings should consider adolescents' use of online communication platforms as part of their maturation.

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Appendix A

The Social Networking Usage Questionnaire

Sr.no.	Statements	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rare	Never
1	I use social networking sites to become more sociable.					
2	I use social networking sites to keep in touch with my relatives.					
3	I use social networking sites to seek help from my teachers.					
4	I use social networking sites for getting jobs related information.					
5	I use social networking sites to share new ideas.					
6	I use social networking sites to create my social identity					
7	I prefer using social networking sites to attending social gathering.					
8	I use social networking sites to get information regarding current social					
9	I use social networking sites for online academic group discussions.					
10	I use social networking sites for reading news.					
11	I use social networking sites for sharing pictures.					
12	I use social networking sites to do research work					
13	I use social networking sites to learn about my curricular aspect					
14	I communicate with my friends via social networking sites in preparation for exams.					
15	I use social networking sites to get relief from academic stress.					
16	I use social networking sites for watching movies.					
17	I use social networking sites for collaborative learning.					
18	I use social networking sites to solve my academic problem.					
19	I use social networking sites to look at funny sharing.					

Appendix B

Adolescent Cyber-Victimization Scale

Never	Once or twice	Fewtimes (between 3 to 5 times)	Several times (between 6 to 10 times)	Manytimes (more then 10 times)
1. Someone insulted or ridiculed me in social networks or groups like WhatsApp to really hurt me.				
2. Someone called my cellphone and hung up to bother or frighten me.				
3. Someone used threats to make me do things on the Internet or smartphone that I did not want to do(like recording myself on video, giving money, doing bad things).				
4. Someone told my secrets or revealed personal things about me in social networks or groups (WhatsApp, snapchat . . .).				
5. To make fun of me, someone made or manipulated videos or photos of me and uploaded or distributed them on social networks or by smartphone.				
6. Someone logged into my profile or accounts and I could not avoid it.				
7. Someone pretended to be me saying or doing bad things on the Internet.				
8. Someone purposely created a webpage, a forum, or a group just to make fun of me and criticize me in front of everyone.				
9. Someone put my cellphone number on the Internet and said bad or false things about me so that people would call me and get me into trouble.				
10. Someone took my smartphone and used it to send photos, videos, or mean messages to others to get me into trouble with them.				
11. Someone criticized me or made fun of comments, photos, or videos I uploaded to social networks or groups like WhatsApp				
12. Someone created a false profile on the Internet with my personal data in order to impersonate me saying or doing bad things.				
13. Someone ignored and did not answer messages or things I shared in groups or social networks, just to make me feel bad.				
14. Someone provoked me in social networks or groups by insulting or taunting me to make me angry and cause a big argument				

15. Someone eliminated or blocked me from groups to leave me without any friends
16. Someone stole my photos, videos, or private conversations and uploaded them or sent them to others.
17. Someone changed my password to social networks so that I could not access them.
18. Someone sent me taunting messages to bother and annoy me.

Appendix C

Ethical Determination of the Study

Informed Consent

I invite you to participate in this research which will take about 15 to 20 minutes of your time.

The research is on relationship between "Social media usage and cyber victimisation"

Your response to this survey will be anonymous and will be used only for academic purposes. Your participation in this study is voluntary.

There is no time limit. Your responses will be used for research purpose only and the responses will be always kept confidential.

nhawkarami@gmail.com [Switch accounts](#)

Not shared

* Indicates required question

Informed Consent

I understand that taking part is my choice. I understand that I can change my mind and leave the study at any time and I do not need to give a reason for leaving.

I understand that the care that I receive now and in the future will not be affected by whether or not I take part in this study.

I understand that this research will be published in a specialist academic journal. I understand that the results will not have any information that allows anyone to identify me.

By pressing YES to this form, I voluntarily consent to participate in this research * study

Yes

No

[Next](#)
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[Clear form](#)